

The City of Harappa: An Architectural and Archaeological Study of the Indus Valley Civilization

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ABSTRACT

Harappa is one of the oldest and most important cities of the Indus Valley Civilization. This report explains how the city began, how it was planned, and what archaeologists have discovered from its ruins. Harappa grew from a small farming village into a large, well-organized urban center with straight streets, strong brick houses, drainage systems, wells, and granaries.

The study also describes Harappa's trade networks, writing symbols, burial practices, and building materials. Many objects such as figurines, seals, pottery, and weights found at the site help us understand the daily life and culture of its people. The report also discusses the reasons why civilization slowly declined, including environmental changes and shifting river systems.

KEYWORDS:

Archaeological Excavation, Urban Planning, Architectural Heritage, Indus Script, Drainage Systems, Settlement Patterns

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Introduction:

On the bank of river Indus, Indus civilization developed which later came to be known as Indus valley civilization. Early Harappan Phase (3300 BCE-2600 BCE), Mature Harappan Phase (2600 BCE-1900 BCE), and Late Harappan Phase (1900 BCE-1300 BCE) are the three phases in which the Indus Civilization evolved. It was one of three early civilizations of the East and South Asia, along with ancient Egypt and Mesopotamia, and was the most widespread.

Harappa is located at Sahiwal District, Punjab, Pakistan

Harappa excavation:

Scholars have been aware of the huge, mounded ruins of the ancient city of Harappa, one of the major sites of the Indus Valley civilization, for more than a century. The remains of one of the earliest towns in the world, Harappa's ancient ruins, have been inhabited for approximately 5,000 years, and the current, vibrant city of Harappa still occupies one-third of the site. Harappa were constructed with baked bricks. Although baked brick looting, which started in the 1850s for Lahore Multan railway, severely damaged most of the site, there is still a large amount of archaeological material that must be completely investigated. The mysterious archaeological artefacts are the only thing we must help us solve the riddle of this ancient civilization because the brief inscriptions of the Indus writing have not yet been deciphered. A broad variety of artefacts that were discovered during excavations in the 1920s and 1930s are now dispersed across museums in Pakistan and India. It is necessary to study and preserve terracotta figurines, carved seals with enigmatic inscriptions, and many tools and ornaments. And regrettably, the early excavators neglected to properly preserve the newly exposed architecture, allowing salt erosion and weathering to cause it to collapse. Pakistan's government and Department of Archaeology and Museums were left with the enormous responsibility of conserving and maintaining the work when the country gained independence in 1947, the huge burden of preserving and caring for the work left by earlier excavators was left to its government and the Department of Archaeology and Museums. In 1966, a brand-new site museum and specialized artefact storage spaces were created at Harappa, but funds for site preservation were short. Despite this situation, residents at the museum were able to affordably repair and preserve several of the structures using resources and craftspeople that could be found nearby.

Discovery of Indus valley civilization:

The oldest records of Harappan ruins were first traced to the Charles Masson book (narratives of various journey in Baluchistan, Afghanistan, and Punjab) written in 1842. In 1856 a British road-engineer named William Boynton ruthlessly dug down these precious remains in search of brick for a railway line which

he was laying from Multan to Lahore. During the process several antiquities were found which were either destroyed or taken away by the laborers. As they continued to work, some of the laborers discovered many fire-baked bricks lodged in the dry terrain. There were hundreds of thousands of uniform bricks, which seemed to be quite old. The laborers used those bricks in the construction of Multan Lahore railway line. Then the site was first briefly excavated by Sir Alexander Cunningham in 1872-73, two decades after brick robbers carried off the visible remains of the city. He found an Indus seal of unknown origin. In 1920 and 1921, Indian archaeologist Daya Ram Sahni oversaw the excavation of the Indus valley site at Harappa. However, John Marshall published the first report on Harappan excavations on March 29, 1921.

Civilization was initially discovered in 1921 at Harappa in the Punjab region, and then in 1922 at Mohenjo-Daro, which is located close to the Indus River in the Sindh region. As Harappa was the first site to be excavated, the civilization also known as the Harappan Civilization

About Harappa city:

In Punjab, Pakistan, close to the Ravi River and 88 kilometers north of the Arabian Sea, Harappa has a long and eventful history that dates back more than 5,300 years. It was simply described as a destroyed city when it was found in 1826 by Charles Masson, a British army deserter disguised as an American engineer. Scholars are just now starting to understand the complex steps that enabled it to flourish and grow, over 170 years later. Our current understanding of Harappa is the result of hard archaeological study carried out by various academics over many seasons of excavation and analysis. We

know that the first people to live in Harappa built a tiny agricultural village on the shore of a lake close to the historic Ravi River 3300 BC based on the most recent excavations at the site. Additionally, this area was excellent for agriculture as for access to rich hunting and fishing grounds.

It is said that Harappa has been the home of about 23,500 residents who lived in sculpted houses that had flat roofs, all made of sand and clay. The earliest village occupation was characterized by small mud-brick buildings. Gradually, the village grew into a town, and eventually the town became one of the four largest cities of the Indus Valley civilization.' Spread out over 150 hectares (370 acres), the archaeological site comprises several low mounds and three high mounds that rise more than fifteen meters above the surrounding plain. The urban phase of the Harappan occupation, dating to between 2600 and 1900 B.C represents the cultural, economic, and political integration of an area that was twice the size of ancient Mesopotamia or Egypt. The large urban centers of this civilization consisted of administrative, ritual, and residential buildings made primarily of baked brick and equipped with elaborate drainage facilities for removal of wastewater and rainwater. The people living in the cities developed extensive trade networks for obtaining raw materials and distributing foodstuffs and finished goods. Specialized technologies of metalworking, lapidary, and ceramics were perfected to make elaborate ornaments and specialized tools that were used locally or traded to distant lands. A highly standardized system of stone weights was developed for trade and possibly taxation. These weights were used in all the settlements of the Indus Valley, and many have been found at sites in Oman and even in Mesopotamia. Texts from Mesopotamian

cities state that onions, cotton, hardwoods, pearls, peacocks, and monkeys were imported from the land of Meluhha (Sumerian name of Indus valley civilization). The Indus cities in return obtained a range of goods that included raw materials, copper, gold, woolen items, and perfumes. Although the Indus traders left many clues to their presence in Mesopotamia, such as weights, seals, and trade goods, there is no concrete evidence of Mesopotamian traders residing in the Indus cities.

The ruling elites of the Indus cities developed a distinctive form of writing that was used on seals, trade goods, pottery, and even personal objects. This writing remains a mystery even though careful archaeological studies are helping to develop a new understanding of how writing was used in the Indus Valley. However, the writing has not yet been identified, it is extremely difficult to reconstruct accurately, the economic, religious, or political systems of the Indus cities.

Most scholars agree that the Indus cities were organized under some form of government that ruled through a combination of religious and economic control. There is little evidence of an extensive military establishment, and it is important to note that there are no representations in the archaeological record of people at war with each other. Surely there was conflict and most of the cities were surrounded by massive mudbricks or stone walls for defense.

The only context in which physical aggression is depicted is on seals or tablets that show a man fighting a wild animal, usually a bull or water buffalo. Several seals show a deity grappling bull trampling a human. Many of the technologies, such as bead making, shell working, glazed faience and terracotta ceramic production, metallurgy, and even architectural forms continue into the later cultures of the subcontinent. The standardized system of weights established in the Indus cities reemerges during the subsequent Early Historic Period around 300 B.C. and continues to be used in traditional trading even today.

Trade:

The Harappans had traded with ancient Mesopotamia, especially Elam, among other areas. Cotton textiles and agricultural products were the primary trading objects. The Harappan merchants also had procurement colonies in Mesopotamia as well as which served as trading centers.

The planning of Harappa city:

The similarities in plan and construction between Mohenjo-Daro and Harappa indicate that they were part of a unified government with extreme organization. Both cities were constructed of the same type and shape of bricks. The two cities may have existed simultaneously, and their sizes suggest that they served as capitals of their provinces. In contrast to other civilizations, burials found in these cities are not elaborate; they are more simplistic and contain few material goods. Remains of palaces or temples in the cities have not been found. No hard evidence exists indicating military activity, though the cities did contain fortifications.

Town planning:

IVC was an urban civilization. That means, IVC was a city-based culture, indicates that towns served as the center of all activity. In comparison to other contemporary civilizations, town planning was the IVC's most significant characteristic.

An upper citadel and a lower town made up the city's two separate parts. On the western edge of the cities stood the Citadel, an elevated area. It might have been inhabited by a member of the elite. There would be settlements populated by commoners on the eastern side. Brick walls surrounded the towns.

- grid structure

In cities, houses were arranged according to a grid layout. The streets were parallel and at right angles to one another. The main streets were almost 10 meters wide - wide enough for two bullock carts or elephants to pass each other.

- Drainage System

The city received an excellent closed drainage system. Every home had its own soak pit and drainage system that was connected to the general drainage system. Every street had brick-built sewers running through it. To clean and clear them, they were covered and had sewers at regular intervals. The Indus people carried a perfect underground drainage system as a result.

- Granaries

The grains were probably kept in these granaries in a safe manner for emergencies or as a source of income. Air ducts provided ventilation for them. There are two rows, each with six granaries, in Harappa.

Burials at Harappa city:

Excavations at the archaeological site of Harappa, Pakistan in 1987 and 1988 uncovered the remains of at least 92 individuals (84 adults and 8 children), although only 19 were complete skeletons in primary contexts. The remains of skeletons are displayed in the Harappa Museum.

The enigmatic Indus script.

The mysteries of Egyptian and Mesopotamian society can be explored because we can read what their priests, rulers, and educated elites wrote. In the Indus Valley, however, no bilingual tablets and texts have been found, and there is no continuity between the Indus script and later writing systems.

The Indus Script is a collection of symbols. They have been found in artifacts. Archaeologists have found 400 different symbols on seals, tablets, ceramic pots etc. However, the writing system of the Indus Valley Civilization has not been deciphered yet. The ancient Indus script appears to have developed locally, though there may be connections with earlier forms of writings in Iran according to some scholars.

In addition, the Indus script is not an alphabetic script but uses more than 400 different types of graphic symbols. Some of these signs are simple lines or dots combined with geometric shapes. Other signs appear to represent stylized animal and human forms or stylized objects and tools. Each sign probably represents a word or syllable, though in some contexts they may refer to a complete sentence. Indus writing is found on a wide range of objects and in various mediums and styles. The most common form is scratched onto pottery, indicating that many merchants and possibly even some potters were literate.

Building Materials

The main materials used were sun-dried and burnt bricks, which were made in molds of 1:2:4 ratios. Easy availability of wood for burning meant baked bricks were used in abundance in Harappa and Mohenjo-Daro. Mud mortar and gypsum cement are also in evidence, and mud plaster and gypsum plaster are also found to have been used. Mud mortar is most evident at Harappa.

Major findings at Harappa city:

- Piece of Pottery with Indus Script
- Cubical Limestone Weight
- Glazed earthenware pottery
- Copper Bullock cart
- Granaries
- Coffin burials (Only founded in Harappa, now in Dholavira)
- Terracotta Figurines

Decline of Indus valley civilization:

The Indus Valley Civilization began to fall around 1800 BCE, however the precise reasons for this are still up for debate. One account claims that the Indo-European tribe known as the Aryans attacked and conquered the Indus Valley Civilization. In later societies, many artefacts of the Indus Valley Civilization have been found, indicating that the civilization did not die abruptly because of an invasion. On the other hand, several experts believe that the collapse of the Indus Valley Civilization was brought about by natural processes, including geological and climatic conditions. The Indus Valley area is likely to have experienced a series of seismic disturbances that led to earthquakes, changed the course of rivers, or made them dry up.

Wheeler, who was Director-General of the Archaeological Survey of India from 1944 to 1948, posited that many unburied corpses found in the top levels of the Mohenjo-Daro archaeological site were victims of war. The theory suggested that by using horses and more advanced weapons against the peaceful Harappan people, the Aryans may have easily defeated them. Yet shortly after Wheeler proposed his theory, other scholars dismissed it by explaining that the skeletons were not victims of invasion massacres, but rather the remains of hasty burials. Wheeler himself eventually admitted that the theory could not be

proven, and the skeletons indicated only a final phase of human occupation, with the decay of the city structures likely a result of it becoming uninhabited.

Present day Harappa site:

Harappa was a fortified city in modern Pakistan. The city is about 150 hectares. There is a museum on the left side right after entering the Main gate. All the artefacts discovered during the excavation are placed in this museum, which included a wide variety of cookware tableware and adornments. They had a belief in life after death; they thought they would use same adornments and cookware when they resurrect that is why they buried with their ornaments and vessels. Their cookware permit of clay evaluating that modern science after latest research had also determined made of clay are useful for human health. Taking exit from museum there is employee residency of archaeological department at left side and ancient Harappa site is on the right side. There is a tomb of Baba Noor shah Wali Ullah. He was famous because his height was nine yards according to people but if we look at the skeletons found during the excavation, all skeleton was of normal height. An old mosque was discovered, and people called it as Eid gah, as it is close to the tomb it might have association with Baba Noor shah wali Ullah. This mosque was built during Mughal era.

The Harappa city has few ruins left, and the ruins shows that the city have two parts: elite people live in citadel, and the common people live in lower town. It has some granaries which was used as the storage area for crops and after the excavation of burials it is find out that they believe in life after death, so they buried their people with cookware and jewelleries and some of the bodies were half, it shows that when their people were died they place them near the trees so, animal eat their flesh and after that bury those bodies. Every artefact which was found during the excavation was placed in the museum.

References

- Cartwright, M. (2015). *Harappa: An overview of Harappan architecture & town planning*. World History Encyclopedia.
- Kenoyer, J. M. (1998). *Ancient cities of the Indus Valley Civilization*. Oxford University Press.
- H.-M. Archaeological Project. (n.d.). *Skeletal paleopathology at Harappa*
- Masson, C. (1842). *Narrative of various journeys in Baluchistan, Afghanistan, and the Punjab* (Early travel notes on Harappa).